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Country report on Egypt

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INTRODUCTION

It could be argued that of all the countries in the world, none has a history and tradition richer than Egypt. As early as human civilizations have existed, man has taken advantage of the fertility of the region and congregated around the river (Elnasharty, 2020). The world has changed since then, and Egypt has moved on from the traditional agricultural based economy on which nations of the past were built, but it remains a key player in the economic and political state of the world.

This essay will look into the current state of Egypt's economy, using sources to state its key sectors and other factors upon which it is built, including any potential weaknesses or vulnerabilities and the analysis of the implications of a global pandemic and the war in Ukraine. In addition, we will see how the country is faring in its key economic indicators, such as GDP growth and inflation, but also look into issues seemingly less obvious but unmistakably as important, such as economic equality levels between the sexes and classes. Doubtless these issues will have consequences that will affect Egypt and its large population for many years to come; so, we will also investigate some policies which are being implemented by the World Bank and suggest some which could yet be implemented to grow Egypt's economy and improve the quality of life for those who live there.

SECTION 1 – Egypt's Macroeconomic State

Egypt is the largest Arab country and Africa's second-largest economy by GDP (IMF, 2023), accounting for 12.5% of continental GDP in 2021 (OECD et al., 2021). Before the COVID-19 pandemic, Egypt's economy was expanding quickly, and it has continued to grow ever since always maintained a growth.

The nation has experienced a process of steady structural transitioning during the last few decades. More specifically, Egyptian's effort to shift their production from agricultural to industrial sector started in 1950s. Since then, industrialization has been seen as a solution to the land scarcity as well as a way to increase incomes.

Egypt has had three essential resources at its disposal to promote industrialization. Firstly, its population increased to the 13th largest in the world today from the 21st largest in 1960, which fueled domestic demand. Moreover, it benefited from its advantageous location between Africa, the Middle East, Asia, and Europe, and the Suez Canal is located there from which about 10% of global trade passes through (Hafez and Madney, 2020). Furthermore, Egypt boasted a sizable textile industry, which is an essential part of the country's output still today. In the beginning of the 19th century, cotton output increased significantly and became the primary raw material used by a number of Egyptian enterprises. The government implemented an industrialization strategy, including strongly relying on state-owned firms, which is responsible of the industries that exist in Egypt today. According to the International Finance Corporation (2023), the "IFC is joining forces with the Government of Egypt to boost private sector participation in the economy – helping to increase competitiveness, create jobs, and improve living standards for Egyptians."

Egypt's economy is heavily reliant on exports, which include crude oil and petroleum products, fruits and vegetables, cotton, textiles, metal products, and chemicals. The Suez Canal, a crucial global shipping lane, is a significant source of revenue and plays a vital role in Egypt's trade dynamics. The trade balance of Egypt is typically characterized by a deficit, where import expenditure often exceeds exports. The Central Bank of Egypt reported that the volume of Egypt's foreign trade during the fiscal year 2022/2023 was about \$110.407bn, consisting of \$70.783bn in imports and \$39.624bn in exports (Mounir, 2023). This situation is partly due to the country's need to import essential items such as wheat and other food commodities. However, efforts have been made to diversify the economy and enhance export capabilities, particularly in non-oil sectors, to improve the trade balance.

Figure 1.1: Egypt’s GDP PPP Growth (The World Bank, 2024)

Egypt’s has experienced strong growth in economic output in the past 30 years, and now sits as the second largest economy in Africa by GDP, behind only Nigeria (IMF, 2023). Figure 1.1 illustrates the high average growth rate in GDP that has resulted in 294% increase in GDP PPP.

Figure 1.2: Egypt’s GDP per capita PPP and HDI growth (GDPpc - The World Bank, 2024 and HDI - UNDP, 2022)

Figure 1.2 illustrates how Egypt’s recent strong growth has translated into improvements in living standards, with GDP per capita more than doubling in this period. This has been reflected in HDI

data, with Egypt’s HDI classed as “high” at 0.731 in 2021 (United Nations Development Programme, 2022).

However, Egypt still heavily relies on sectors like agriculture and tourism. Much of the country still lives in poverty, “According to United Nations figures, some 20 to 30 percent of the population live below the poverty line.” (Genoni, 2023). This is in part due to uneven development that has led to unequal wealth distribution across the country, especially between those who live in urban and rural areas. Not far from the wealthy areas, urban areas, a remarkable number of Egyptians live with overcrowded and substandard housing, insufficient access to food or clean water and without access to proper education or healthcare. The “1% of the highest-income Egyptians received 19% of the total national income, while the 50% of the lowest-income Egyptians received only 17.2%”, in 2019.

In Egypt, wealth distribution is marked not only by regional disparities between urban and rural areas but also significant gender-based inequities. Egypt as a country has one of the highest gender wage gaps as it is ranked in the 129th position among 149 countries (Hamad, 2023). Moreover, women represent only 18% of Egypt’s employment (The World Bank, 2022) which shows the disparity between genders in the workforce. Women’s labor force participation is low opposite to the unemployment which is high especially comparing to men. Although, in recent years, the gap in education between the two genders has narrowed, but women still earn less. The main obstacles that manage to keep unemployment rate for women high, despite the slight decrease the past years as we see in Figure 1.3 is their household responsibilities, the persistent wage gaps, and most importantly the inappropriate attitude, and sexual harassment in the workplace.

Figure 1.3: Unemployment rate by gender in Egypt

SECTION 2 - How Egypt's economy has evolved and dealt with global shocks

International conflict and the COVID-19 pandemic are two global shocks that have challenged the Egyptian economy in recent times. This can first be seen by the COVID-19 pandemic, which officially reached Egypt in February 2020 (Medhat and El Kassas, 2020), that posed a major economic challenge to all economies. However, Egypt was among the limited number of economies in the world to maintain a positive GDP growth rate in 2020 (IMF, 2021). By rapidly implementing several successful measures, Egypt was able to prevent major economic consequences. This was despite the sudden drop in tourism, which at the time of the pandemic accounted for 12% of GDP and 10% of all employment, as well as a sharp decline in domestic activity and tax revenues.

Egypt entered the COVID-19 crisis in a relatively fortunate economic position as the country made many reforms prior to the pandemic. On November 11 in 2016, the IMF approved an amount of about US\$12 billion under the Extended Fund Facility for a three-year period to support an economic reform program (Lagarde, 2016). As part of this program, Egypt implemented numerous reforms recommended by the IMF. This included moving to a floating exchange rate system to eliminate currency overvaluation and accumulate foreign exchange reserves. This system left Egypt much better prepared for the economic shock that it would face, as a floating currency acts as an automatic stabiliser, dampening economic fluctuations. This is because it allows the value to adjust based on market forces, and tends to depreciate as economic activity slows down, which in turn stimulates demand for domestic goods. In addition, the January 2017 IMF report called for “strong fiscal consolidation to ensure public debt sustainability” as part of the program’s four key pillars. This resulted in the introduction of a VAT, increasing tax revenues by 2.5% of GDP (IMF, 2017). Importantly, Egypt set to use part of the fiscal savings to strengthen social protection programs, such as cash transfers to the elderly and low-income families.

These steps allowed the government to launch a comprehensive pandemic response faster (IMF, 2020). For example, they were able to provide financial fiscal support which included relief to businesses and workers in the worst affected sectors, such as tourism. In addition, the Central Bank of Egypt cut policy interest rates by 400 basis points which, alongside other measures, helped to smooth credit flow to support economic activity (IMF, 2021).

However, Egypt’s successful response to the pandemic was also heavily attributed to aid from the IMF. Egypt was able to access around \$8 billion in financial support, firstly through the Rapid Financing Instrument (RFI). The IMF states that the RFI is designed to provide “prompt financial assistance to any IMF member country facing an urgent balance of payments need.”. In May 2020, Egypt was able to access \$2.8 billion in emergency financial assistance (IMF, 2021), which ensured the government had sufficient foreign currency, used to manage and stabilise the currency through buying and selling in the foreign exchange market. The IMF also approved access to US\$5.4 billion in the following 12 months through their Stand-by-Arrangement. This program helped support the economy in the wake of the virus, with the included economic policies helping to strike the difficult balance between shielding the economy from the COVID-19 shock and ensuring debt levels remain sustainable to maintain investor confidence.

Figure 2.1: Comparison of Egypt’s unemployment rate (ILO, 2024)

Figure 2.1 highlights the success of the aforementioned reforms prior to the pandemic, reducing unemployment from 13.1% to 7.9% in Egypt (ILO, n.d). The success of the reaction to the pandemic is also evident with the unemployment rate in fact decreasing since the pandemic in 2020. In this period meanwhile, both the MENA (Middle East and North African) and global average increased relatively significantly, emphasizing its success compared to most other economies.

The second recent global shock affecting Egypt was the Russian invasion of Ukraine in February 2022, with Egypt having close ties to both countries involved. The connection is most notably formed through food imports, in particular wheat with Egypt being the world’s largest importer of the grain (Magdy, 2023) and ‘around 85 percent’ (Gadallah and Mamdouh, 2023, p.4) of this wheat being imported from Russia and Ukraine in the 5 years prior to the conflict. The conflict created food shortages, leading to a large increase in food prices and thus high levels of inflation. Figure 2.2 presents a record food price rise of ‘73.6%’, and a record high inflation rate of ‘38%’ in September 2023.

Figure 2.2: Egypt’s inflation and food inflation rates in 2023 (CAPMAS Egypt, 2024)

Therefore, it can be seen international conflict has placed an intense strain on Egypt’s food security, and with over 92% of low-income households having children (HIECS, 2019; cited by Gadallah and Mamdouh, 2023, p.5), the country could be in danger of suffering critical levels of child malnutrition. Additionally, tourism revenue and foreign direct investment are two other sectors in which the economies of Russia, Ukraine, and Egypt are interconnected. It is estimated around 30% of tourists traveling to Egypt are from Ukraine and Russia and FDI from Russia makes up 30-60% of Egypt’s total FDI in energy (Gadallah and Mamdouh, 2023, p.7). Consequently, Egypt has suffered from a depletion of foreign currency, further intensifying the existing issue of currency devaluation created by the COVID-19 pandemic. A weakened Egyptian pound increases the price of imports, pushes inflation higher, and exacerbates the developing food security problem being faced by the country.

In response to the poor food security and high inflation created by the Russia-Ukraine conflict, the Egyptian government is in the process of implementing and expanding policies to tackle these growing, contemporary issues. The Takaful and Karama Program (TKP) was introduced in 2015 (World Bank, 2018) and aims to provide poor, vulnerable families with a monthly allowance for food. Food insecurity has led the government to significantly increase its funding into social protection networks and the TKP. From 2022/23 to 2023/24, the budget allowance has been increased by 48.8% to EGP 529.7 billion (Khalid, 2023), conveying the heightened focus on the issue. However, government funding has not solely been sufficient in supporting this program and three World Bank loans, amounting to USD 1.4 billion, have been required (Enterprise, 2022). Despite this, the success of the program cannot be disputed with the scale rising dramatically from an initial 63,000 households supported to now approximately 5.2 million families (El Tawil, 2023).

Furthermore, from an International Food Policy Research Institute (IPRI) study in 2018, it was concluded the TKP reduced the likelihood of families falling below the poverty line by 11%, increased food consumption by 8%, and lowered child malnutrition in children under 5 by 3.7% (Hteit, 2023). Despite the severity of global shocks in the last 5 years suggesting an increase in the poverty rate should've occurred, Egypt's rate has fallen from 32.5% in 2017/18 to 27.3% in 2023. Thus, there is some success in the way Egypt has dealt with recent global shocks.

However, the TKP's success will remain limited as long as inflation rises faster. In 2022, families receiving the funding only saw a 1.5% increase in their benefit compared to a 24.4% inflation rate. The most recent evaluation of the study by the IPRI in 2018 shows the success seen 5 years ago will likely have significantly diminished notwithstanding the substantial government and World Bank injections. However, a report is yet to surface to cement this theory. Therefore, it can be seen the Egyptian economy has had a very mixed reaction to the recent global shocks affecting the world. This is through positives such as economic growth during the pandemic and the Takaful and Karama program, but also negatives like the drastic rise in inflation.

SECTION 3 - Labour Market challenges in Egypt

For the past 30 years Egypt has been entering into increasing numbers of significant free trade agreements with influential countries and organizations, but these efforts have not borne fruit. They are still suffering from difficulties within their labour market, such as high levels of informal employment, high wage inequality and low female and youth employment (Tillian et al., 2023, p.4). Here we will investigate the sources of these problems, explain why they are unsustainable for Egypt's economy in the short and long-run and suggest possible solutions to alleviate these difficulties.

The informal sector is part of the economy where economic activity is not covered by formal arrangements. In Egypt, the lack of opportunities in the formal private sector and the growth of the labour force exceeding that of job creation has led to considerable informality rates. Today, over 90% of working Egyptian youth (aged 15-24) are employed informally (Khalid, 2023).

These rates have severe repercussions, such as depriving the government of potential tax revenue. According to the Egyptian's Cabinet Information and Decision Support Center, informality accounts for a loss of approximately EGP 400 billion in taxes annually. These earnings could alleviate Egypt's notable external debt and budget deficit.

On a similar note, the existence of this sector is inequitable to tax paying firms and creates unfair competition between regulated and unregulated firms, hampering long-run economic growth.

Furthermore, frequent cash-based transactions characterize the country's shadow economy, as most workers lack access to credible financial services. These transactions, as well as the sector's size and complexity, impede the government's ability to regulate the informal, and formal, economy which is growing more precarious.

Still, the country's informal market contributes significantly to national income: 40% of GDP (Khalid, 2023). Likewise, the sector's low barriers to entry can be beneficial to small firms, as they can conveniently resort to informal activity in times of economic instability.

Today, the government has taken initiatives towards the integration, not eradication, of the sector. Egypt has prioritised collecting more taxes from the sector, as taxes account for over 75% of revenues allocated for the 2023/2024 national budget.

Nevertheless, economic analyst Khaled Abu Shad criticizes that Egypt is not doing enough to integrate this economy and that it should "*consider offering tangible benefits to incentivize informal establishments to legitimize their activities*". Banking expert El-Beih adds that the tax authority could enable them to "*self-report their revenue and pay marginal tax for a preliminary period*".

We will now shift our focus to how the COVID-19 pandemic has exacerbated Egypt's labour market challenges. When COVID hit Egypt in February 2020 there was an increase in unemployment and economic inactivity (not being employed nor searching for work). The International Labour Organisation's (ILO) study (based on a survey) shows that unemployment

rose by 3% and inactivity by 4% in June 2020. Still, as mentioned in section 2, unemployment has fallen since the pandemic.

More private sector workers, those in individual firms or nongovernmental organisations, have transferred into inactivity and unemployment (10%) compared to public sector employees (5%). This hampers the already slow growth of private sector employment.

Job formality played a crucial role in maintaining jobs during the COVID crisis. According to a World Bank report, COVID caused half of Egypt’s informal workers to lose their jobs between 2020 and 2021. Similarly, in June 2020, 64% of workers in the informal sector suffered from lower wages compared to only 21% of the formally employed workers (ILO, 2021).

Figure 3.1: Efficiency-wage model

In Figure 3.1, the increased unemployment (A to B) reduces the reservation wage (where workers are indifferent between being unemployed or employed), as the expected duration of unemployment rises should workers lose their jobs. At B, firms lower wages (W_1 to W_2) for the same output (E_2) and a higher markup, which is the amount remaining after sales not given to workers.

Formal workers usually have a fixed wage rate and number of working hours, unlike informal employees, and hence have steadier income levels. Though informal workers supposedly recovered from the reduced wages, despite being more vulnerable to income declines, the ILO revealed that the average hours worked per week was lower in June 2021 compared to 2020 (Assaad et al., 2022).

In contribution to the informal sector, the persistence of high youth unemployment in Egypt is a continuous challenge. In 2021, 19.7% of individuals aged 20-24 were unemployed in Egypt. In addition to weak development and labour productivity, unemployment is costly due to the erosion of the tax base and increased welfare fees.

A study published by UNICEF in July 2023 found that the highly educated youth in Egypt were more susceptible to unemployment than those with no education. University graduates are struggling as they wait for employment that corresponds to their qualifications rather than searching for work. UNICEF also suggests that the incongruity between the skills acquired at school and those demanded by employers leave the *"youth unequipped for the labour market"* (UNICEF, 2023).

To address this, Egypt focuses on ameliorating the quality of technical and vocational education (TVE) in response to the shifting market demands. For instance, Applied Technology Schools and Dual Education System. However, not everyone can access TVE institutions: young women and rural residents. Promoting online education with the Ministry of Education and Technical Education's online platform, developed during COVID-19, could enhance inclusivity.

It seems likely that the issue surrounding Egypt's labour market is that its productivity of labour is not growing at the same rate as other countries experiencing high growth. One way that Egypt can attempt to boost its productivity is by encouraging innovation and entrepreneurship, which in turn will encourage competition and efficiency. The World Bank is aware of this and has undertaken a \$200 million project which they have entitled the "catalyzing entrepreneurship for job creation" project (The World Bank, 2021). The essence of this project is to make credit and funding more easily available for "MSMEs" (micro, small and medium-sized projects). Clearly this removes a large barrier to entry into a lot of markets and will encourage competition. The World Bank claims that, as of December 2023 "188,000 entrepreneurs, 43% of them women, have received financing through the project. This led to the creation of about 380,000 private sector jobs." They also claim that these figures show the strong desire Egyptians have for entrepreneurship, but this is a good time to highlight a potential problem. Egyptians may just be taking advantage of easily available credit without necessarily being in a good position to create an efficient firm that will survive in the long run. If a significant portion of the economy is made up of small firms led by inexperienced entrepreneurs, this has the potential to be unstable as time exposes the inefficiencies of these firms. This may lead to widespread job loss and uncertainty in the long run.

Nonetheless, it seems very likely that this project will benefit Egypt's economy in the long run. In the short and medium term there may be some instability as new firms rush into the market to capitalize on cheap credit, but the fierce competition these new firms will encounter will purify the market and ensure that only the most efficient firms survive in the long-run. However, it should be noted that these firms would not have even been able to exist without the project due to any high start-up costs. Furthermore, it is likely that most Egyptians would rather work for a firm started and run by a local rather than a faceless entrepreneur from outside Africa.

It is also possible that Egypt's exports are contributing to their labour market problems. Egypt has an obvious lack of diversity among its exports, with oil making up almost a quarter of total exports, with the World Bank noting that "since 2010, none of the non-oil exports have managed to take off" (Robertson, Vergara, Kokas and Lopez-Acevedo, 2021). Such lack of diversity makes them vulnerable to exogenous factors, such as changes in oil prices and even a pressure among many firms by their governments and consumers to switch to renewable energy sources, reducing the demand for oil in the long run.

A large supply of such a widely required resource can also lead to complacency in reducing costs and increasing productivity. To ease their labour market problems, it would seem that higher participation in Global Value Chains (GVCs) may help. GVCs refer to the process of producing a good or service distributed among different countries. A paper published by the IMF studies the effects of GVCs in Estonia and highlights a potential link between the engagement in GVCs and labour productivity (Banh, Wingender and Gueye, 2020). Another paper published by the IMF highlights the positive relationship between participation in GVCs and income per capita (Raei, Ignatenko and Mircheva, 2019). Whether one variable is causing another or the two are simply correlated is difficult to say, but from their findings we can see the positive relationship between the two. Additionally, the World Bank claims that "Countries that embrace them (GVCs) grow faster, import skills and technology, and boost employment." They also note that Egypt has a relatively low engagement in GVCs compared to similar countries with similarities to them and suggest that this is causing them problems within their labour market.

Still, one doesn't need to look back far to see a potential problem GVCs. A crisis such as a pandemic will and has shown how this can make countries particularly vulnerable (the paper above was published before COVID-19), the consequences of which have already been highlighted earlier. This may provide an explanation as to why the consequences of COVID-19 were not as severe for Egypt. Even ignoring this however, you can see why an Egyptian could be skeptical to follow this course. First, they are told to lower trade barriers and embrace free trade to encourage economic growth. They obediently did so and are still seeing the same problems. Now they are told that this was a good start but that if they really want to see economic growth they need to join in and embrace GVCs. Can we be certain that this is not just a repeat of what we were told in the past? Maybe not, but the evidence from Estonia does seem to suggest that their productivity of labour will grow, which is a common factor among all nations experiencing economic growth.

CONCLUSION

Overall, Egypt faces economic challenges such as poverty, inequality, and economic inactivity. To combat food security, the country implemented the Takaful and Karama Program (TKP) which has successfully provided monthly food allowances to over 5 million households. However, the reliance on substantial government funding and loans from the World Bank obstruct its effectiveness and intensifies Egypt's external debt. Inflation further diminishes the program's success, as allocated allowances struggle to keep pace with rising prices, and so lose value.

Similarly, the World Bank's project facilitating credit access for micro, small, and medium-sized enterprises (MSMEs) aims to boost entrepreneurship and labour productivity. While it has created jobs and fostered competition, accessibility to credit may be taken advantage of, and inexperienced entrepreneurs are less qualified to create efficient firms. Hence, this project might not bolster competition.

Engaging in Global Value Chains (GVCs) could unlock Egypt's untapped labour potential, providing skills through diverse tasks and boosting employment and growth. However, skepticism persists due to concerns about vulnerability during pandemics and instability. Despite these limitations, increased GVCs engagement would lead to an improvement in labor productivity.

Egypt relied on its expanding population, geographical position, and textile industry to undergo a structural transformation from agriculture to manufacturing, facing challenges from reliance on tourism and agriculture, despite efforts to diversify exports and improve trade balance. Global shocks such as the COVID-19 pandemic and the Russian invasion of Ukraine impacted Egypt, but some of the government policies and World Bank loans softened the effects, and even reduced poverty rates. Still, over 90% of Egyptians aged 15-24 operate informally, leading to tax revenue losses and regulatory challenges. Efforts to address youth unemployment through technical and vocational education face obstacles, as labour market demands and acquired skills of employers do not align.

This discussion of Egypt's macroeconomic state was based on recently published articles and official governmental data. It should be noted these sources have limitations and figures may not be entirely accurate due to differences in data collection techniques, data size, and how representative survey samples are, limiting the credibility of our analysis.

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